

Studies on Dithiocarbamates: Part V. Kinetic Studies on 3,5-Disubstituted tetrahydro-1, 3,5-thiadiazine-2-thiones

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Kinetic studies on the titled compounds under acidic and alkaline pH have been carried out; and the corresponding activation parameters ($\Delta G^\ddagger$, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ & $\Delta S^\ddagger$) suggest that the mode of acid-degradation is different from that of alkaline-degradation. Mechanisms consistent with observed data have been suggested.

Vast amount of work has already been reported¹ on the antimicrobial properties of dithiocarbamates(I) and their related oxidation products, thiuram disulphides (II); and several hypotheses have been advanced² to explain their biocidal activities. The essential structural feature in these compounds is the occurrence of NC (:S) group, and, consequently, multitude of compounds, both cyclic and acyclic, had been screened³ as potential bioicides.

Although different kinds of views exist⁴ regarding the exact nature of the toxicants, nevertheless, toxicity of cyclic systems like rhodanines (III) and 3:5-disubstituted tetrahydro-1, 3, 5-thiadiazine-2-thiones (IV), could only develop through *a priori* fission of cyclic systems. It is indeed surprising to find that until quite recently⁵ not much attention has been paid to the physico-chemical properties of IV(R & R'=alkyl or aryl), although extensive evaluation on their biocidal activities had been reported⁵.

Recently, it has been shown⁶ that the thiadiazine system(IV) displays two characteristic bands around 250 and 290 m μ in the UV region, but the nature of the absorption

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curves depend on the type of substituents at N_2 and N_3 positions (and hence the absorption curves are of some diagnostic importance). Further, information regarding the rate of fission is also vitally important to derive the maximum benefit out of a product. To this end our kinetic studies on IV, mainly 3-aryl-5-methyl type of compounds, are reported here.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Appropriate thiadiazines have been previously described⁴. Constant pH was maintained by using a series of buffers; pH, 4.15–6.07, acetate buffer; 7.1 & 8.45, phosphate buffer; 9.1 and 9.8, carbonate-bicarbonate buffer.

Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out with Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer in 1 c.m. matched quartz cells.

Rate Measurements: As shown in fig. 1, both the 250 and 290 m μ bands are affected by gradual hydrolysis of IV, but the end-products exhibits negligible absorption at 290 m μ . Further, λ max for all the compounds under investigation fall within 290 ± 5 m μ . Hence, in all cases progress of hydrolysis was followed by measuring the change in absorbance at 290 m μ .

Hydrolysis of dilute solutions were studied in 10% (V/V) ethanol at 0.01 ionic strength maintained with added KCl. All reactions were carried out in stoppered volumetric flasks maintained at a constant temperature ($T \pm 0.5^\circ$) bath. Solutions were equilibrated at appropriate temperatures prior to mixing and the flasks were withdrawn at suitable intervals to measure the absorbance values.

In all cases, the initial concentrations were so chosen as to give initial absorbance values around 1.0 and the concentration varied from 1.19×10^{-4} mole to 0.7×10^{-4} moles/l. The pseudo first order rate constants (K_{ob}) were estimated from the graphical plots of,

$$\log (D_t - D_\infty) = \log (D_0 - D_\infty) - \frac{k_{ob} \cdot t}{2.303}$$

when, D_0 = initial absorbance

D_t = absorbance after a time 't'

D_∞ = absorbance after complete hydrolysis.

The calculated pK value (7.46) of the protonated species of IV ($R=Ph$, $R'=CH_3$) was obtained by subjecting the absorbance data at $t=0$ (at pH 4.15, 7.1, 9.8) to Henderson-Hasselbalch expression. The activation parameters were calculated from the respective Arrhenius plots.

RESULTS

The kinetic data for a series of 3-aryl-5-methyl compounds (IV, $R=aryl$, $R'=CH_3$) at a constant pH (7.1) are presented in Table II; but in one instance, (IV, $R=Ph$, $R'=CH_3$), detailed investigation was carried out over a wide range of pH (4-10) and the corresponding data are summarised in Table I. Since 3,5-dimethyl compound (IV, $R=R'$

$=\text{CH}_3$) is reported⁶ to possess various biocidal activities, kinetic data on this compound is also included in Table II for the sake of comparison.

Typical first-order plots of a representative member are shown in fig. 2. That the observed rate constants are directly proportional to hydrogen ion concentration (H_3O^+) in the acidic region is clearly shown in Fig. 3, and the corresponding rate-law is governed by

$$k_{ob} = 1.84 \times 10^8 [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+], \quad \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

and it is reasonable to assume that other members of the series would behave similarly under acidic conditions.

In Tables I & II, the activation parameters for the hydrolysis are listed. It is instructive to note that $\Delta S^\ddagger$ for the dimethyl compound (IV, $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{CH}_3$) has considerably higher negative value compared to the 3-aryl analogues. Further, linearity of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (Fig. 4) for the hydrolysis of these compounds could be observed only on the alkaline side of pH.

TABLE I

The observed rate constants and the activation parameters for the hydrolysis of 3-phenyl-5-methyl tetrahydro-1, 3, 5-thiadiazine-2-thiones at varying pH and temperatures

Serial No.	pH	Temp °C	$k_{ob} \text{ Sec}^{-1}$	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ Kcal/mole	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal.	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ Kcal/mole at 25°C
1.	4.15	24	6.03×10^{-3}	7.38	-43.90	20.46
		32	8.43×10^{-3}			
		49	1.59×10^{-2}			
2.	5.08	24	2.56×10^{-3}	7.64	-44.84	21.01
		32	3.96×10^{-3}			
		49	7.67×10^{-3}			
3.	6.06	24	3.26×10^{-4}	8.71	-45.09	22.15
		32	5.76×10^{-4}			
		49	1.25×10^{-3}			
4.	7.10	24	3.84×10^{-5}	14.79	-28.93	23.41
		32	8.17×10^{-5}			
		49	2.63×10^{-4}			
5.	8.45	24	2.29×10^{-5}	10.98	-43.05	23.81
		32	4.41×10^{-5}			
		49	9.60×10^{-5}			
6.	9.1	25	2.07×10^{-5}	9.15	-51.76	24.58
		32	3.48×10^{-5}			
		49	6.49×10^{-5}			
7.	9.8	22	1.63×10^{-5}	6.10	-59.88	23.94
		32	2.14×10^{-5}			
		49	3.98×10^{-5}			

DISCUSSION

Examination of results in Table I indicate that at any given temperature the observed rate is appreciably faster in the acidic pH. Although pH-rate (log k_{ob}) profile exhibits a sigmoid curve (not shown) over the entire pH range, yet under moderately acidic

condition (pH 5-7), as in Fig. 3, k_{ob} varies linearly with (H_3O^+) . This can be reconciled with the following scheme involving attack of H_2O on the protonated species in equilibrium with the substrate (A):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate of reaction} &= k [AH^+] [H_2O] \\ &= k.K [A] [H_3O^+] \\ &= k_{ob} [A] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{hence, } k_{ob} = k.K. [H_3O^+] \quad \div \quad (2)$$

From equations (1) and (2),

$$k.K. = 1.84 \times 10^4 \text{ litre/mole,}$$

where k is the second order rate constant and K is the equilibrium constant. From the calculated pK value of IV ($R=Ph$, $R'=CH_3$), $K=6.4 \times 10^4$ litre/mole, sec^{-1} . This compares favourably with reported⁷ second order rate constants found in connection with acid hydrolysis of substituted Δ^2 -thiazolines.

TABLE II

Rate constants and activation parameters for hydrolysis of substituted tetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine-2-thiones at various temperatures at a pH of 7.1

No.	Substituents		Temp.	$k_{ob} \text{ Sec}^{-1}$	ΔH^*	S^*	ΔG^*
	$R'(N_3)$	$R'(N_3)$	$^{\circ}C$		Kcal/mole	eu	Kcal/mole at 25 $^{\circ}C$
1.	Methyl	Methyl	24	2.82×10^{-6}	11.43	-44.82	24.79
			37	8.98×10^{-6}			
			49	1.73×10^{-5}			
2.	Phenyl	Phenyl	24	3.20×10^{-6}	15.25	-32.36	24.89
			37	9.40×10^{-6}			
			49	2.45×10^{-5}			
3.	Phenyl	Methyl	24	3.84×10^{-5}	14.79	-28.93	23.41
			32	8.17×10^{-5}			
			49	2.63×10^{-4}			
4.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	,,	24	4.65×10^{-5}	14.76	-28.67	23.30
			32	1.02×10^{-4}			
			49	3.57×10^{-4}			
5.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	,,	24	3.00×10^{-5}	13.73	-32.91	23.54
			37	8.70×10^{-5}			
			49	1.98×10^{-4}			
6.	<i>p</i> -hydroxy-Ph	,,	24	2.71×10^{-5}	18.91	-17.61	23.56
			32	7.29×10^{-5}			
			49	2.97×10^{-4}			
7.	<i>p</i> -chloro-Ph	,,	24	3.84×10^{-5}	17.60	-19.57	23.42
			37	1.30×10^{-4}			
			49	2.44×10^{-4}			

The acid decomposition of dithiocarbamates (I) are believed to proceed by proton addition according to the following equilibrium reactions⁸.

The structure 'B' is the reactive form which decomposes to give the rate constant (k) and the reverse rate (k₂) is insignificant. The overall reaction is, therefore, controlled by pH of the medium and this indeed was found to be the case during acid hydrolysis of IV. Lack of any significant change among the activation parameters coupled with high negative values for ΔS* also suggest that decomposition of IV in the acidic region involves the same reactive species, mainly B as above, and pH dependence arises through initial protonation.

Fig. 1. Change of absorbance of IV (R=Ph and R'=CH₃) with time. I: pH, 5.08; T=23°, λ=290 mμ. II: pH, 5.08; T=23°, λ=250 mμ. III: pH, 7.1; T=32°; λ=290 mμ.

Fig. 2. Typical first-order plots of acid (I & II) and alkaline (III) hydrolysis of IV (R=Ph, R'=CH₃)

The above facts, therefore, tend to suggest that the acid decomposition of IV probably involves the following steps:

The same compound (IV, R=Ph, R'=CH₃) show a linear relationship (ΔH* vs ΔS*) only on the alkaline side. But a gross change in the mechanism of hydrolysis is indicated by a sharp change in ΔH* around pH 7.0; and better stability in stronger alkaline medium is reflected in high negative values for ΔS*. It appears that at higher alkaline pH, the rates constants are essentially constant, 2.0 × 10⁻³ sec⁻¹ at 25°, and this kind of pH independent hydrolysis is known to occur with 2-methyl-5,6-dihydrothiazine⁹, 2-methyl-oxazoline⁹ and Schiff's bases derived from aliphatic and aromatic amines.¹⁰

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Analysis of data presented in Table II show that for a typical 3: 5-dialkyl diaryl compound the rate constants are fairly close. But change of 3-methyl to 3-aryl group causes considerable acceleration of rate of hydrolysis. However, the presence of a substituent in 3-aryl group, although limited in number, is not properly reflected in the kinetic data. In fact, attempted correlation between rate constants and substituent effect (Hammett or Taft) was not successful. It is, therefore, reasonable to suspect that steric requirements¹¹ of the transition state play a predominant role in the formation of the kinetically important species. Additional evidence in support of this contention is found in the initial increase in absorbance (pH 7.1) followed by gradual decrease in absorbance values in accordance with the first order law (Fig. 1).

These findings are consistent with the known¹² behaviour of amides or esters where initial step involves reversible addition of hydroxide ion to the substrate as shown below.

Fig. 3. Dependence of observed rate constant on hydrogen ion concentration.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\Delta H^{\ddagger}$ vs. $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$ for different compounds at constant pH 7.1 (I) and at different pH for the same compound (IV, R=Ph; R'=CH₃) (II).

The linear correlation between $\Delta H^{\ddagger}$ vs $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$ (Fig. 4) suggests¹³ that in all cases under review, the probable reaction mechanism is the same. In spite of this situation, further scrutiny of data reveals that $\Delta H^{\ddagger}$ is not sensitive¹³ to the same extent as $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$. This could be understood only in terms of hydration or water structuring¹¹⁻¹³ of the transition state. Thus, with p-chloro- or p-hydroxy compounds, (No. 6 & 7, Table II), possibilities of solvation are better than with the p-ethoxy compound (No. 5). Consequently, desolvation at the transition state may be reflected in somewhat lower negative values for $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$. The recorded data confirms this expectation.

The importance of this kind of solvation or water structuring have been recently invoked^{11,12} to explain the experimental data and the nonlinear Hammett relationship may be interpreted in terms of a cancellation¹⁴ of a substituent effect on account of hydration at the rate determining step.

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The thiadiazines are regarded as synthetic mustards and their efficiency is believed to be due to the formation of isothiocyanates¹⁵. These informations, therefore, allow us to draw the following mechanistic path of degradation under neutral or alkaline condition.

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